

Growth and yield attributes of rice varieties under intermediate deepwater conditions (up to 80 cm). Cuttack, India, 1988.

Treatment	Cross	Flowering date (DAS) ^a	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-gram weight (g)	Grain yield (kg/15.8 m ² plot)	Straw yield (kg/m ²)
Tall varieties									
CN573-2-21	Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2	2 Nov (161)	170	81	3.22	146	25.8	3.71	6.17
CN579-363-3-1	Jhingasail/Jaidhi 2	4 Nov (163)	160	90	2.99	139	25.8	3.48	5.50
ET10002	Jaladhi 2/Pankaj	2 Nov (161)	167	72	2.93	136	25.6	3.70	5.26
IET10006	Patnai 23/Pankaj	2 Nov (161)	176	68	3.26	149	25.5	3.49	5.25
Semitall varieties									
CR292-805I	Pankaj/Mahsuri	20 Oct (148)	129	91	2.65	130	21.2	2.81	4.34
CR687-2-10	Savitri/Jagannat//CR333	15 Nov (174)	137	68	2.37	151	20.1	2.15	3.50
CR1030	Waikoku/CR210-1014	25 Oct (153)	138	63	2.50	145	19.1	2.28	4.13
Hathipanja (check)		28 Oct (156)	143	65	2.81	99	30.1	2.48	3.92
Semidwarf varieties									
CR210-1016	Pankaj/Jagannath	28 Oct (156)	98	60	2.18	123	19.0	1.79	2.34
CR260-171	CR151-791/CR210-1014	2 Nov (161)	120	52	2.32	126	22.2	1.63	2.82
CR527-18-2	Agahania/Savitri	24 Oct (152)	121	64	2.47	101	26.1	1.72	2.92
Kalinga 3	AC540/Ratna	1 Aug (68)	113	71	0.89	37	18.9	1.01	1.16
SE	-	-	5	5	0.22	10	0.2	0.30	0.43
N fertilizer (kg/ha)									
0	-	-	135	62	2.52	115	23.2	2.20	3.47
40	-	-	142	76	2.74	131	23.4	2.83	4.41
SE	-	-	1	2	0.08	3	0.1	0.06	0.12

^aDAS =days after sowing.

fewer grains per panicle, for a yield similar to that of other semitall cultivars with relatively finer grain types. CR687-2-10, although it flowered very late (mid-Nov), produced a yield similar to that of semitall cultivars that flowered in mid-Oct.

Application of N hastened flowering by 4-6 d but increased stem borer incidence by 42%.

Grain yield had a significant positive correlation with plant height at maturity ($r = 0.904^{**}$), panicle weight ($r = 0.869^{**}$), and grains per panicle ($r = 0.665^{**}$).

Panicles per m² (considered a major yield attribute of medium-duration dwarf varieties under shallow water and irrigated conditions) had no significant relationship with grain yield under excess water ($r = 0.572$ ns). Panicles per m² was low (less than 100/m²), which ultimately led to heavier panicles, and that influenced yield most.

These results indicate that tall, elongating cultivars with good panicle size that flower during the first week of Nov are better suited to intermediate deep water conditions. Panicle number appears to be the limiting factor for higher yields. □

Grain quality

Attaining higher volume expansion in popped rice

M. K. Bhashyam and T. Srinivas, Central Food Technological Research Institute, Mysore 570013, India

Popped, puffed or expanded, and flaked rice products are prepared widely throughout major rice consumption areas in India. Appropriate varieties account for nearly 10% of the total rice produced. Parameters characteristic of the popping quality of rice include maximum proportion of popped grains, volume expansion (ml of popped fraction from 100 g rough rice), and separation of husk from the product.

The factors associated with popped rice quality may be variety, machinery,

and processing techniques. We studied the optimum conditions for several processing variables, using a grain roaster.

Volume expansion was maximum when grains with 14% moisture were roasted at 275 °C for 40 s with sand of 0.35-0.60 mm size, at a ratio of 1 rice:2 sand.

Using these standard conditions, we screened 28 varieties for popping quality. Six varieties with volume expansion 900-1,300 ml were considered good poppers. The remaining varieties with volume expansion 20-765 ml were poor poppers.

In samples of seven varieties harvested late, volume expansion ranged from 80 to 770 ml. This reduction appears to be due to the number of cracked grains in the late harvested samples (see table). Cracking-resistant and cracking-susceptible varieties

harvested at optimum moisture content (22-24%) did not show significant differences in popping quality. Late harvesting at 16-17% moisture content, however, resulted in a greater reduction of volume expansion in crack-susceptible than in crack-resistant lines.

In four varieties, germinated or parboiled rough rice showed 50% reduction in volume expansion, probably due to loosened husk and other factors related to changes brought about during these processing operations. Samples of seven varieties stored for 12 mo under ambient conditions showed enormous improvement in volume expansion.

Popular varieties Intan (volume expansion 1,300) and FT 12, a selection from Vani (volume expansion 935), proved to be good poppers with maximum husk separation. They can be recommended for yield and improved

popping quality. CRHP-8 and White Puttu were good poppers, but are agronomically poor. They could be used as donors for good popping gene.

The recommended practice of harvesting at optimum moisture content for high yield and good milling quality also applies to high volume expansion. □

Effect of variety, harvest moisture, and grain cracking on popping quality of rough rice.^a

Variety ^b	Volume (ml) of popped fraction ^b			Cracked grains (%)	
	Fresh rough rice	Stored rough rice	Late harvested and stored	Optimally harvested	Late harvested
				Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Inran	970	1300	—	—	—
CRHP-8 (waxy)	900	1040	770	0.4 ± 0.5	6.00 ± 1.2
FT-14 (CS)	870	1000	80	10.2 ± 1.0	50.00 ± 3.1
White Puttu (waxy)	—	965	—	—	—
FT-12 (CR)	55	935	590	0.2 ± 0.4	4.2 ± 0.8
FT-125	880	900	—	—	—
Y-4	—	765	640	0.4 ± 0.5	4.2 ± 0.8
S-701	—	755	—	—	—
ES-18	—	750	—	—	—
IR20	—	715	—	—	—
FT28 (CS)	630	600	170	1.8 ± 1.3	23.0 ± 2.4
Madhu 43	—	600	—	—	—
FT19 (CR)	215	555	320	0.4 ± 0.5	4.0 ± 0.7
Halubbulu	500	530	—	—	—
FT1	320	465	—	—	—
FT2	170	450	—	—	—
Vani	—	410	—	—	—
Bharani	—	345	—	—	—
IET4699	—	390	—	—	—
S199	—	270	—	—	—
Puspha	—	270	—	—	—
Purple Puttu (waxy)	—	230	—	—	—
Pusa 150	—	335	230	1.0 ± 0.7	12.0 ± 1.5
Rajmudi	—	235	—	—	—
Madhu	—	200	—	—	—
Pankaj	90	75	—	—	—
FT199c (completely chalky)	—	20	—	—	—
Sona	—	20	—	—	—

^a Av of duplicate values. ^b CS =cracking susceptible, CR = cracking resistant.

Procedures for quality selection of aromatic rice varieties

R. F. Reinke, L. A. Welsh, J. E. Reece, L. G. Lewin, and A. B. Blakeney, Yanco Agricultural Institute, Yanco, NSW, 2703, Australia

Aromatic or fragrant rice varieties have an associated flavor. The Basmati rices of Pakistan and India and the jasmine-type rices of Thailand are the aromatic cultivars commonly encountered in world trade.

Changing immigration patterns have created a demand for aromatic rices within the Australian domestic market, presenting the local rice industry with a challenge to breed a temperate climate-adapted aromatic cultivar.

The physicochemical properties of Australian non-aromatic long grain rices are similar to those of some traditional good quality Asian aromatic rice varieties (see table). The fragrant varieties usually have soft to intermediate cooked grain texture and high elongation on cooking.

During the last 8 yr, we have used a number of fragrant lines in our breeding

program. Quality selection has concentrated on subjective odor and taste tests, as well as on normal tests for appearance and for milling and eating quality.

Selection for fragrance has some unique demands. While the major chemical components of fragrance have been identified, we do not use a gas liquid chromatography technique to quantify the active compounds, for fear of selecting against other odor or taste components traditionally associated with high quality, aromatic rices. We believe that taste is as important as aroma, and that these characters vary in type as well as in intensity. Consequently, taste analysis is the most reliable approach for new variety selection.

To ensure selection of pure fragrant lines, the presence of the fragrant character must be subjectively assessed and quantified at each stage of development. Fortunately, the character is present in vegetative material as well as in grain and can be determined by tasting the lower sections of tillers at about the flowering stage. This makes it possible to harvest only those lines with the highest probability of having aromatic grain.

Testing procedures allow experienced taste panels to assess breeding lines for aroma and flavor characteristics. Because of the limited quantity of seed available in early generations, polishing

Physicochemical properties of some fragrant rices and some Australian nonfragrant varieties.

Variety	Milled rice property		
	Amylose (% db)	Alkali spreading value	Gel consistency (mm)
Khao Dawk Mali 105 (Thai aromatic)	19	7.0	94
Milagrosa (Filipino aromatic)	24	4.7	60
Seratus malam (Indonesian aromatic)	24	6.0	40
Kulu (Australian nonaromatic)	19	7.0	100
Inga (Australian nonaromatic)	21	6.8	100
Pelde (Australian nonaromatic)	22	6.8	100
Goolarah (Australian aromatic)	21	6.5	100